

PARADIPLOMACY AND INDIA: ROLE OF STATES IN INDIA-GULF RELATIONS

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Abstract:

In the literature of international relations this practice, where local and regional governments involve in making countries' foreign policy is known as “constituent diplomacy”, sub national diplomacy, or “Paradiplomacy,” this concept was first emerged in the 1970s and later in the 1980s, the group of North American scholars, John Kincaid, Ivo Duchacek, Panayotis Soldatos, Hans Michelmann, Earl Fry developed a theoretical frameworks in this field that has been widely used in contemporary studies on paradiplomacy today. The paper examines the scope for Paradiplomacy in India-GCC relations, as current government has been appreciating the significance of cooperative as well as competitive federalism. Further, the paper attempts to highlight the contribution of Indian states such as Kerala in building India's relations with the Gulf countries. Apart from the economic Paradiplomacy in India-GCC relations, the paper also explores beyond economic Paradiplomacy such as soft power and Indian Diaspora and its contributions in strengthening India's relations with the GCC states.

Keyword: India-Gulf Relations, Paradiplomacy, Regional governments

Introduction

Political scientists and international relations theorists have observed in recent decades that the significance of non-state actors in international relations has grown in response to the expansion of multinational firms and unrestricted capital flows. Further, since the end of the Cold War, the central government's legitimacy as the sole international actor in the field of diplomatic relations has been questioned. Thus, it is crucial to examine the emergence of new global actors for contemporary scholarship in the field of social sciences. Because without understanding these changes, it is difficult to provide a clear picture of the scenario that is occurring in contemporary foreign policy and in the

internal affairs of states. In the early 1970s, in their co-edited work *Transnational Relations and World Politics* Robert Keohane and Joseph Nye first argued about “transnational relations” among non-state actors like multinational corporations (MNCs). As a direct result of this development, more opportunities have become available to discuss new players in international relations. And then studying the activities of subnational governments at the international level has grown and been discussed widely in the academic discourse of comparative politics as well as international relations. So, in the literature of political science and international relations this practice, where non-central governments engage with foreign countries is commonly known as “Paradiplomacy” concerns with the ability of subnational governments to engage in foreign policy and challenges the traditional notion that only sovereign nation-states with the authority of central governments may engage in diplomatic relations (Tewari, 2017). The major imperative that supports the concept of para-diplomacy is the financial reasons and a significant surge in people-to-people synergies at multiple levels irrespective of national borders. Many scholars believe that generally subnational government deals in so-called “low politics” matters that include economic, cultural or social affairs. For example, “opening trade and cultural missions abroad, signing treaties and agreements with foreign state and non-state actors, participating in international networks of regional cooperation and sometimes even challenging the official foreign policy of their central governments through their statements or actions (Tewari, 2017).”

In the case of India's position in paradiplomacy, it falls under the categories of those countries where sub-national governments are not treated as ‘legitimate international actors. And Constitution of India has clearly distributed the legislative powers between the Union and states (Article 246). Legislative power related to foreign affairs came under the Union list, thus the central government has exclusive rights to make laws on matters such as diplomatic, consular and trade representation, participation in international conferences, treaties and agreements with foreign countries and implementation of treaties, agreements, and conventions with foreign countries, foreign jurisdiction and trade and commerce with foreign countries. However, the introduction of Liberalization, privatization, globalization and Economic liberalization weakened the hold of the central government on the financial activities

of the Indian states and the emergence of coalition governments in Indian politics facilitates the regional governments to engage foreign countries in areas of trade, commerce, foreign direct investment, education, and cultural exchanges. Another important reason for this growing influence of state governments on foreign relations could be the political weight of a leader of a particular state and his/her influence on foreign policymaking (Mattoo, & Jacob, 2009). Further, present government also advocates for the regional governments in favor of greater participation in foreign policy – particularly when it comes to fostering economic relationships and attracting foreign direct investment.

Pieces of literature related to paradiplomacy in India are predominantly about states that have borders with India's neighboring countries such as West Bengal's engagement with Bangladesh and the role of Tamil Nadu in India-Sri Lanka relations etc. Thus, there is a need to explore how Indian states have been contributing to strengthening India-GCC relations. and what role Indian regional governments must play in strengthen India-GCC relations. The region is important for India, as India gets most of its energy from the region and around 7 to 8 million Indians live there and send back remittances. This study first investigates the notion and substance of paradiplomacy as it has developed in India during the last several years. and then explores the evolution and progress of paradiplomacy in India and gives a brief introduction to the growing role of sub-regional units in foreign policy making. Further, it explains what role paradiplomacy plays in Indian foreign policy and then examines the scope for Paradiplomacy in India-GCC relations, as the current government has been appreciating the significance of cooperative as well as competitive federalism.

Paradiplomacy: Academic and Theoretical Discussions

Defining paradiplomacy is an increasingly difficult task because of its recent inception in the literature of political science and international relation. “Although there is no single binding definition of Paradiplomacy, it generally refers to the international activities and foreign policy capabilities of a sub-state of political units” (Jackson, 2017). Stefan Wolff describes paradiplomacy as a “foreign policy capacity of sub-state entities, their participation, independent of their metropolitan state, in the international arena in pursuit of their own specific international interest.” (Wolff, 2007). In other words, Para-

diplomacy is a way for sub-national units of a sovereign state to interact diplomatically with another sovereign state or its sub-national units to further their own interests, which are often related to economic, cultural, or social issues. In other words, in their external engagement, Subnational governments generally deal with “low politics” that include environmental issues, investment promotion, cultural and educational exchange etc. On the other hand, “high politics” is represented by a central government's diplomatic and military security agenda (Kamiński, 2018). Apart from this term “Para-diplomacy” the external diplomatic activities of subnational governments are also known as “constituent diplomacy,” “regional diplomacy,” “sub-state diplomacy,” “micro-diplomacy,” “multilayered diplomacy,” “catalytic diplomacy,” “proto-diplomacy,” “post-diplomacy” and so on (Kuznetsov, 2014, p.25). However, Lecours (2002) makes little distinction between protodiplomacy and paradiplomacy although considering the former as most ambitious form of the latter, he argues “Protodiplomacy, unlike more common forms of paradiplomacy, clearly involves attempts at influencing the policies of sovereign states.” In this paper, I will prefer “paradiplomacy” to all the mentioned terminologies as (Kuznetsov, 2014) argues that for the last two decades, academic discourse has already acknowledged “paradiplomacy” as an umbrella term that may include all types of regional and politically motivated actions for reaching “economic, cultural, political, or any other type of benefits, the core of which consists in self-sustained actions of regional governments with foreign governmental and non-governmental actors”. Moreover, the external activity of subnational governments is now not limited to federal states nor to established democracies (Cornago, 2010) as initially, there used to be a strong presumption that paradiplomacy was conducted by constituent units of those countries that have federal systems such as the USA and Canada or semi-federal states like Spain. As Lecours (2002) argues “The more power a regional government has, the better it is positioned to act beyond national borders.” By saying this, he was talking about federal systems, which technically share sovereignty and give their areas a head start on getting international authority. Moreover, it was widely believed among scholars that the existence of paradiplomacy requires democratic government. As Kuznetsov argues (2014) that no meaningful federalism is possible without genuine democratic power sharing. The case of the USSR

served as evidence to support this claim. Therefore, it was considered that paradiplomacy would not exist in non-democratic states in accordance with this line of reasoning. However, now constituent units of unitary states have also been conducting it such as Japan and even non-democratic states such as China. Thus, the case of Chinese provinces that have been actively in paradiplomacy, proves that even in non-free political systems, constituent diplomacy does exist, although it presumably operates according to different principles than in plural democracies (Kuznetsov, p. 42, 2014).

In recent years, the inception of concepts such as Twin towns or sister states and successful efforts at “city diplomacy” by cities like São Paulo has drawn the attention of researchers to include the municipal units in paradiplomacy. In addition to that Twin-town or sister-city is a notion in which cities establish their own international connections based on mutually beneficial agreements. “These pairings can be conducted for cultural or economic exchanges, which, in turn, are beneficial to both cities/towns” (Tewari, & Pant, 2017). Since 1988, Brazil has seen significant growth of paradiplomacy at the municipal level. When the new constitution approved the decentralization of the Brazilian Federation. At the federal level, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs has created a distinct administrative department to facilitate interaction with municipalities and federal states. Interestingly, all 26 government departments in São Paulo have foreign partnerships or projects, particularly in infrastructure construction. Both the United Kingdom and the United States have formal bilateral relations with São Paulo (Ratna, 2013).

While, talking about the aim of paradiplomacy “it be can range from bringing in a decentralized dimension to international debates to the internationalization of domestic issues by bringing regional issues onto the global stage, promoting trade, tourism, cultural ties and even post-conflict reconciliation to local political activism being sought for international support. Subnational relations can also be conducted to promote and attract investments seeking region-specific economic advantages” (Tewari, & Pant, 2017). Through paradiplomacy the following goal can be achieved:

“In the economic sphere, it can lead to international funding, as well as foreign investments and increased exports of locally produced goods. In the political sphere, agreements can empower state public policies

and disseminate best practices as well as carry the needs of subnational governments to the international system—through networks of cities and bilateral agreements, for example. In the cultural sphere, subnational governments can seek/sign agreements with foreign countries to increase tourism” (Jha, 2014).

While taking into consideration the institutionalization of paradiplomacy in the Indian context, Shah, & et.al, (2023) have listed three institutional purposes that paradiplomacy serves in India, which are: (i) “the promotion of cooperative and competitive federalism; (ii) the pursuit of commercial and cultural diplomacy by states; and (iii) the enhancement of bureaucratic efficiency.” These three institutional reasons coincide with three phenomena in the Indian political system (with considerable overlap among them) Firstly, economic liberalization and globalization have created opportunities for Indian states to engage in foreign policy decision-making, especially in the area of economic policymaking and cultural diplomacy. Secondly, the emergence of regional political parties in the states and the emergence of coalition governments at the Union level has promoted political decentralization in India and brought fundamental changes in foreign policy as well. And thirdly, the advocating of the present government for an assertive foreign policy that would involve the states including setting up of the “States Division” under the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) to work with state governments in 2014. In addition to this, in order to address institutional mechanisms in the field of paradiplomacy, Tewari, (2017) suggested that the Effective institutional procedures must be developed by the central government to promote paradiplomacy in the country, firstly the creation of consulates or consular offices in individual states. secondly the setting up of federal foreign affairs offices under the supervision of the MEA. In order to accomplish the Center's objectives, the staff members assigned to these regional offices may be taught to deal with security-related concerns more effectively. Hence, the enhanced coordination through regular consultations and bureaucratic interactions between the MEA and local offices can be effective in promoting the goal of paradiplomacy.

The Historical Development of Paradiplomacy Studies

Taking into consideration the historical studies of paradiplomacy, historically, the evolution of paradiplomacy studies from its beginning till today has been categorized by Kuznetsov, (2014, pp.34-42) into four

stages. He argues that the studies of paradiplomacy have begun during the period of 1970s. As this was the period when political scientists seriously noticed the emergence of regional governments as new actors in international affairs. According to him since this period was predominantly based on the case study analysis, thus the case study of Canadian provinces (independence movement in Quebec) and US states (“New Federalism” policies introduced by the Nixon administration) in international affairs was carried out.

The period of the 1980s was crucial because paradiplomacy studies became a self-sustained branch of research in contemporary political science. AS scholars such as Ivo Duchacek, Hans Michelmann, John Kincaid, Panayotis Soldatos and others predominately from North America tried to construct paradiplomacy and develop theoretical patterns in order to comprehend the origins and implications of constituent diplomacy in federal systems.

From the 1990s the global expansion of paradiplomacy studies occurred. Since this period witnessed the end of the cold war and its related incidents like the fall of the Iron Curtain and changes in other global world politics like the rapid consolidation of the European Union as a new supranational organization a result, paradiplomacy studies expanded outside North American academia. The fourth phase has begun in the 2000s. In this phase, the scholarly interest in paradiplomacy geographically spread worldwide as the position of non-Western countries in world politics and the global economy has improved, the field gained new academic influence among researchers from Latin America, Africa, and Asia. For example, Fritz Nganje (2014) talked about the paradiplomatic efforts of South African provinces and their contribution to the democratization of Pretoria’s foreign policy. In the case of Indian scholars such as Amitabh Mattoo and Happymon Jacob (2009), they study that how the impact of globalization has enabled subnational Indian governments to undertake high-profile investment promotion campaigns abroad. Tomasz and others (2019) explored the role of Chinese provinces in China’s relationship with the EU. During this phase, some studies have also been done about paradiplomatic activities that have been happening in unitary states (Liu, T., & Song, Y, 2020). Earlier it was believed that para-diplomacy—an attribute of federal or semi-federal states—could not exist in a country having the unitary form of government (Kuznetsov, 2014).

Indian states and their para-diplomacy with GCC states: experience and opportunities

While delivering the Lecture at an event on the topic “India and the World” in October 2013 the then BJP's Prime Ministerial candidate Narendra Modi was advocating for redefining the country's foreign policy. He said “India is not just Delhi. And he further stated, “The foreign policy should be decided by the people and not by some politicians sitting in Delhi.” While considering its election manifesto, after coming into power BJP government set up the “States Division” under the Ministry of External Affairs (MEA) to work with state governments in 2014. The aim of the ‘States Division’ is to “serve as the Ministry's single avenue for outreach to states” (Jacob, 2016 & Tewari, 2017). and to coordinate with states and Union Territories (UT) “for further facilitation of their efforts to promote their exports and tourism and attract more overseas investments and expertise” (Jacob, 2016 & Tewari, 2017). Additionally, the “States Division” provides direct briefings to Chief Ministers of Indian states on investment opportunities and international cooperation and sometimes arranges meetings with the target state's ambassador' (Jacob, 2016).

In India, paradiplomacy came into play after 1967, when regional coalition governments increased the autonomy of states. However, it was unusual. It gained momentum after liberalization in the 1990s. For example, in 1992, when the power sector was first opened to private foreign investors, the Maharashtra government entered into an agreement with the Texas electric company, Enron, and General Electric to finance its Dabhol project. The project was started only after the active support of the then central government.

As mentioned earlier, under article 246 the Indian Constitution has clearly distributed the legislative powers between the Union and states and the central government has exclusive control over all matters related to foreign affairs. Interestingly state governments, legally, are not even allowed to participate in any international conferences. However, since the late 1960s the end of single dominated “congress system” and the emergence of coalition governments in Indian politics and with the introduction of Liberalization, privatization, globalization and specifically Economic liberalization in the 1990s the state governments began to play a crucial role in foreign affairs. Another important reason for this

growing influence of state governments on foreign relations could be the political weight of a leader of a particular state and his/her influence on foreign policymaking (Mattoo, & Jacob, 2009). For example, Chandrababu Naidu as Chief Minister of Andhra Pradesh (1995–2004) was proactive in reaching out to the U.S. in the late 1990s and early 2000s. Naidu was able to promote his State, especially the city of Hyderabad, as an Information Technology (IT) hub. President Clinton made it a point to include Hyderabad in his itinerary. Narendra Modi as a Chief Minister of Gujarat (2002–2014) represented Gujarat through the Annual Vibrant Gujarat Summit. He led delegations to several countries including China, Japan and Singapore. Mamata Banerjee Chief Minister of West Bengal Opposed the Teesta River Water Treaty, as well as the Land Border Agreement with Bangladesh. and J. Jayalalithaa the then Chief Minister of Tamil Nadu Pressurized the central government to vote against Sri Lanka at the United Nations on two occasions, in 2012 and 2013(Maini, 2014). Further Kerala Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan has made four visits to the UAE since assuming office in 2016 to propose investment opportunities with the Abu Dhabi National Oil Company and the Abu Dhabi Investment Authority, and other expatriate organizations in Kerala (Mathrubhumi, 2020; Saseendran, 2019).

In addition to that, In the Indian context, paradiplomacy is significant for many reasons. Firstly, since India has many regional political parties so any agreement signed by the Central government cannot be successfully implemented without the cooperation of the state governments, hence making the state governments a part of such discussion can yield better results. secondly, with respect to bordering states, it is imperative for them to have better connections with their neighboring countries. Any dispute that arises between two nations can be fruitfully resolved by engaging the border states in the discussions because most of the time these states either have grievances with or interests in solving disputes with the neighboring nations. one can cite the example of West Bengal in case of Teesta River water issue between India and Bangladesh and example of Tamil Nadu with regards to minority Tamil population residing in Sri Lanka. Thirdly, by Involving states in matters such as investment promotion, cultural and educational exchange, and more, a sense of competition could be fostered among the states, and eventually, this would lead to better governance and would promote Cooperative and Competitive Federalism.

While talking about the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), so GCC is a political and economic alliance of six Gulf monarchies including Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE). It was formed in 1981 uniting with the similar nature of political and economic systems, contiguous geography, common language, and culture, having a strong hold in the West Asian region. India's interests in GCC states are in its energy security, the volume of trade, and the large presence of Indian expatriates. Current estimates suggest that there are around 8.5 million Indians in GCC countries, with over 3 million in Saudi Arabia. This is followed by UAE, with about 2.8 million Indian workers. There are about 923,000 in Kuwait, 316,000 in Bahrain, 600,000 in Qatar, and 796,000 in Oman (MEA GOI, 2016). In conclusion there has been strong, growing, and multifaceted strategic partnership between India and the GCC countries, ranging from energy, trade and investment to counterterrorism and defense cooperation.

While examining the role of states in India-GCC relations some states play a particularly important role in India's linkages with key GCC countries. Kerala is an example because of the large number of Keralites living in Gulf countries. Thus, the case study of Kerala becomes important as Kerala has been influencing as well as strengthening India's foreign policy towards GCC countries. Further, Kerala has vested benefits in coordinating diplomatic relations with West Asian countries more specifically the GCC states as a great number of the state's inhabitants find employment in those lands (Amaresh, (2020). As the state of Kerala—the largest exporter of manpower to Gulf countries. For instance, the state government of Kerala has a Department of Non-Resident Keralites Affairs headed by a secretary-level officer to deal with international affairs such as diaspora and labor matters (Jacob, 2016). In 2004, the government of Kerala suggested the creation of a Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs, in response, the then-UPA government created the same and later the government decided to merge the Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs with the Ministry of External Affairs (Sharma, & others, 2020). While the matter regarding the release of Keralite prisoners from Sharjah jails in the UAE arose in 2017, the Chief Minister of Kerala did not seek any help from the center; rather, he himself invited Sharjah's ruler, Sultan bin Mohammed Al-Qasimi, for a visit to Kerala. As a result the Sultan announced the release of the 149 prisoners from Sharjah jails (Sharma, & others, 2020).

Moreover, during his week-long visit to the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Kerala Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan discussed ways to promote closer economic ties between the UAE and the southern Indian state. Vijayan was in the US for medical treatment and stopped in the UAE on his way back (Maini, 2022). The visit was significant because of the reception he received: Sheikh Mohammed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, Vice President, Prime Minister and Ruler of Dubai, broke protocol and met Mr. Vijayan at the Dubai Expo 2020 venue. Several prominent individuals, including the Chairman of Emirates Airline Group, Sheikh Ahmad bin Saeed Al Maktoum were also present during this meeting. Apart from the Crown Prince of Dubai, the Kerala Chief minister also met with Sheikh Nahyan bin Mubarak Al Nahyan, Minister of Tolerance and Coexistence, Abdulla Mohammed Al Mazrui, Chairman of Abu Dhabi Chamber of Commerce and Industry and UAE Minister of State for International Cooperation Reem Al Hashimy (ANI,2022). Interestingly, the Dubai ruler tweeted in Malayalam, and in a friendly gesture, Kerala CM replied in Arabic. Soon after his meeting with Kerala Chief Minister Pinarayi Vijayan in the Emirates, Sheikh Mohamed bin Rashid Al Maktoum, Vice President and Prime Minister of UAE and Ruler of Dubai wrote in Malayalam “The UAE shares a special relationship with Kerala. Keralites are playing a significant role in the economic and developmental growth of Dubai and the UAE.” In response, the Chief Minister replied to Sheikh Mohamed bin Rashid thanking him through an Arabic tweet. “Humbled by your hospitality and warm welcome,” and he made the case for greater cooperation between Kerala and the UAE and hoped that the latter would support major infrastructure projects in the state. Further, Kerala's diaspora, estimated at one million, constitutes a significant percentage of the Indian diaspora not only in the UAE but in the Gulf region. The state enjoys warm relations with the UAE and there have been several high-level visits by UAE leaders to Kerala and vice versa. Vijayan has visited the UAE three times since assuming office in his first term as chief minister in 2016. Additionally, in order to promote its regional identities and culture, an initiative was taken by the government of Kerala in 2017 during the visit of the ruler of Sharjah H.H. Sheikh Dr. Sultan Muhammad Al Qasimi, to the state when it proposed the establishment of a Kerala Culture Centre in Sharjah (New Indian Express, 2017). This proposed Centre is intended to foster closer cultural ties between Kerala

and the Emirate, which has a large diaspora from the state (Government of Kerala, 2017). While considering the spheres of consular affairs and diaspora engagement, the Kerala Government has initiative taken in its outreach towards the 3.5 million strong Keralite diaspora population residing in the Gulf States (Bywalec, 2018). To address the concerns and welfare of the large diaspora population, the state government has set up a department called the Non-Resident Keralites' Affairs Department, or NORKA-Roots (Wyatt, 2017). The department serves as a kiosk for the Keralite diaspora to interact with the Indian state government, access important information about legal protections and facilitate their rehabilitation on return to the state (NORKA-Roots, n.d.). Moreover, in order to cater to its Gulf diaspora Kerala government has been advocating to launch of its own airline "Air Kerala" to cater to passengers travelling between the state and Gulf Cooperation Council countries (*The Hindu Businessline*, 2018).

Historically, remittances from the Gulf have contributed greatly to Kerala's economic growth. However, in recent years, due to the slowdown in Gulf economies, recent changes in the Gulf economies and the labor market as well as the Covid-19 pandemic, large numbers of migrants have returned to Kerala and remittances have declined remarkably. In 2020, the World Bank estimates a drop in remittances from the UAE to India at a staggering 17 per cent (Maini, 2022). According to new research (Reintegration & Rehabilitation Policies for Emigrants in Kerala: Strategies for a Post-COVID World, n.d.) "In response Kerala government has taken initiative to utilize the skills of return migrants productively for the development of the state is the project called, 'Norika Department Project for Return Migrants (NDPREM)', which helps return migrants to develop sustainable business models for livelihood and offers 15 per cent subsidy."

Another important point is that countries such as Saudi Arabia, UAE, and Qatar have huge sovereign wealth funds which are always looking for good investment destinations. India needs to not only access these funds but build security linkages to secure its energy and its people. In regard, some states have the capacity to invite these GCC countries to invest as Jha (2014) argues that there exist multiple factors that make states such as Gujarat, Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh attractive destinations for FDI.

- (i) They are strategically located, providing easy access to external markets.
- (ii) These states possess the most robust infrastructure with an extensive network of railways and roads and the highest number of airports (international and domestic) in the country.
- (iii) A large pool of high-quality manpower is abundantly available in these states across various sectors.
- (iv) The governments in these states have also been proactive in introducing sector-specific policies for the promotion of investment and growth.
- (v) They have also witnessed the establishment of foreign trade offices by various countries for facilitating mutual trade. (Jha, p. 13, 2014)

Conclusion & Recommendations

Paradiplomacy deals with the foreign policy capacity of subnational governments and challenges the conventional diplomatic relations that fall under the exclusive domain of sovereign nation-states exercised by central governments. Paradiplomatic activities are generally successful in the areas of “low politics” including economic, cultural or social affairs, the same is true in the case of India too. and the matters of “high politics” involving diplomatic and military security agendas fall under the Central/federal governments. Paradiplomacy serves various purposes on the ground that make it desirable. Generally, regional governments depend on Union resources for their operations. But any government has limited resources. Thus, through subnational diplomacy, a regional government can attract FDI. Also, for a country as diverse as India, paradiplomacy offers alternatives to regional governments to develop a development model that meets its local needs.

In India, the involvement of state governments in the realm of diplomacy, particularly economic diplomacy, is increasing. As we know India is a quasi-federal system as it has features of both a federal and a unitary system however, with more tilt towards a unitary system of government. Thus, the Indian Constitution places foreign relations and defense in the Union List in the Seventh Schedule. Nevertheless, states are increasingly participating in foreign diplomacy because of the phenomena of globalization, liberalization and the emergence of coalition governments in Indian politics.

To a large extent, the concept of para-diplomacy has yet to take on a broader meaning in both Indian foreign policy and academia with

respect to India-GCC relations. However, the current administration wants to encourage state governments to develop para-diplomatic relations. As the MEA has formed a “division of states,” the government should adopt better policymaking practices and set precise rules to reap the benefits of sub-national diplomacy. Therefore, the positive involvement of Indian states in policymaking should be welcomed to strategically work through dynamic forms of geopolitics. As mentioned earlier GCC countries have enormous funds in the form of sovereign wealth funds to invest, in this regard, Indian states can play a greater role in attracting foreign investments by creating a conducive environment for investment and trade. India is going through an interesting phase, where it is transforming from a regional power to a global power and has a dynamic foreign policy to support its growth, in this phase states have a larger role to play in the development of the country. Including solving the financial crisis and environmental degradation to attracting investments at a regional level. Interestingly states in India are often better equipped to take diplomatic action in the areas of trade, foreign direct investment, education, and cultural exchanges. Further India is a diverse country with each of the 28 states having its own strategic advantage and opportunities. Thus, States should use their capabilities to take advantage of the globalized market economy for their own development. The role of states in strengthening their economic advantage will be significant in India's ascension to a five-trillion-dollar economy in the coming years. The foreign diplomacy of states, however, is not limited to the economy. They are also important in subjects such as security, environment and resource management that need to be explored by the states.

While considering India-GCC engagement, Indian states can further leverage the potential of paradiplomacy by using overseas Indians. As expats from states such as Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Punjab, UP, Bihar, and West Bengal, and have been living in the gulf states They can play an important role in economic paradiplomacy for their respective states can leverage their capabilities and use paradiplomacy to stimulate economic growth. States may also engage into agreements to promote tourism, cultural exchange, and urban planning. They may also participate in student exchange programmes offered by government colleges and universities in their respective states. These programmes serve as a conduit that brings Indian students into contact with broader platforms or possibilities.

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